

Principals' Total Quality Human Relations Management Skills and Teachers' Pedagogical Output

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ABSTRACT

The study utilizes ex-post facto research design, employing co-relational descriptive survey method on comprising 17,024 population, which includes 16,384 teachers and 640 principals from Bayelsa and Delta States. The sample size includes 812 secondary school principals and teachers from both Bayelsa and Delta States using random sampling technique. The research instrument is a self-constructed questionnaire developed based on the integrated quality management constructs originally formulated by Saraph, Benson, and Schroeder (1989) and information from relevant literatures. The questionnaire "Principals' Total Quality Human Relations Management Skills and Teachers' Pedagogical Output Questionnaire" (PTQHRMTPOQ). To gather responses, the questionnaire employed a Likert 4-point rating scale. The questionnaire was structured into two main sections. Section A aimed to collect background information which included personal details. Section B to assess the Principals' Total Quality Human Relations Management Skills and Teachers' Pedagogical Output in public secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States. The face and content validity of the instrument was assessed through expert judgment. The reliability of this instrument was assessed using both the split-half method and the Cronbach alpha after administering the instrument to a randomly selected groups of forty-five (45) secondary school principals in Edo State, chosen due to its shared historical, geopolitical, social, and economic characteristics with Bayelsa and Delta States, all of which belong to the same South-South Geopolitical zone in the Niger-Delta region of Nigeria. The scores obtained from the responses were tabulated and analyzed which yielded 0.79 reliability coefficient indices. The researcher utilized descriptive statistics, specifically mean scores and standard deviation to address the research question, and the correlation coefficients to determine the existence of relationships among the variables. A mean score (\bar{X}) rating of 2.50 or higher was considered as the benchmark for acceptance. Additionally, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics were applied to assess the significance of the relationship in the formulated hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05. The results were presented and analyzed in tabular form. The findings indicates that although principals are ascetical total quality management human/interpersonal relationship skills has positive significant relationship with teachers pedagogical output in secondary schools in both Bayelsa and Delta States. It was recommended that principals and teachers in secondary schools should shift their perspective on Total Quality Management (TQM) skills, recognizing that they are beneficial not only for businesses but also for educational institutions.

Keywords: Principals', Total Quality Management, Pedagogical, Administration, Teachers' Output, Human Relations

Background to the Study

Total Quality Management (TQM) is a concept referring to all embracing administration, absolute quality administration (AQA), all out quality management, complete quality administration/management, integrative quality management/administration and collaborative quality administration. In this research, these concepts will be used to mean one and the same thing as total quality management (TQM) which emphasizes the integration and coordination of all activities within a work process to continuously enhance quality, transcending final products to encompass diverse aspects, including data/information processes, decisions making, setting of objectives, working out strategies to achieve the objectives, bringing in people, materials, machinery as quality inputs, and quality system outputs.

TQM involves the application of quality management principles within the organization, promoting continuous improvement by all members of the organization. It operates on principles that necessitate the ongoing cooperation of all stakeholders to efficiently satisfy the needs, objectives, and expectations of clients/customers and the community. This is achieved by maximizing the potential of all employees through a continuous drive for improvement (Dalt, Boaden, & Lascelles, 2004).

TQM adopts a management style that places people at the core of its principles and practices, extending its focus beyond organizational boundaries to prioritize the interests of its clientele. It is a quality-centric, customer-focused, evidence-based, team-driven, and seminar-led management approach, aimed at satisfying the organization's clientele while achieving organizational goals.

As emphasized by Umoru (2006:84), TQM encompasses four major components: total commitment to quality, total commitment to students' satisfaction, total commitment to continuous quality improvement, and total commitment of both the program and teachers to each other. TQM represents a comprehensive philosophy for living and working within organizations to drive organizational improvement. This philosophy of quality improvement applies to the education sector, as educating people is considered akin to the business of producing goods and services, both of which involve the management of quality.

The hope is that the findings from this research will provide insights into how Total Quality Management (TQM) can be employed to address the challenges of human relationship to enhance teachers' pedagogical performance. Human relations in the workplace is vital to the output of the workplace which is made up of; the work environment, interpersonal relationship, communication, and staff welfare among others. As emphasized in Anho's (2020) perspective, a conducive work environment is vital as it offers comfort and security for teachers in carrying out their instructional responsibilities and other duties. An optimal work environment empowers teachers to perform their roles effectively and wholeheartedly, ultimately influencing the future success of their students and the broader goals of education. Teachers' salaries and emoluments serve as significant human relations' motivators for their commitment to their profession. Finally, timely and regular payment of teachers' salaries plays a pivotal role in determining their interest, motivation, commitment, and overall productivity.

Pedagogy pertains to the methods and practices of teaching, encompassing educational goals and the strategies used to achieve them. Teachers fulfill the pedagogical role by carrying out various school duties and functions related to teaching. This includes preparing and utilizing class management, selecting suitable teaching methods, delivering lessons, employing teaching resources, and evaluating instruction.

In their analysis of teachers' pedagogical output, Anho et al. (2020) describe it as comprising all the efforts made by teachers to attain the intended educational results for students. This incorporates the degree to which teachers participate in various school activities directed towards the achievement of the institution's aims and objectives. Such activities encompass:

- Establishing well-defined, measurable, and realistic behavioral lesson objectives.
- Improving the preparation and timely utilization of teaching materials.
- Effectively delivering lessons.
- Carrying out proper assessment and grading of student work and assignments.
- Sustaining an orderly classroom environment.
- Nurturing a favorable classroom atmosphere and enforcing discipline.
- Actively engaging in extracurricular activities.
- Cultivating positive relationships with students, peers, and school administration.
- Successfully accomplishing curriculum objectives within prescribed timeframes.
- Employing effective questioning methods.

- Promoting and valuing feedback from students.
- Providing individualized attention to students as necessary.
- Employing current and appropriate teaching approaches.
- Ensuring the achievement of curriculum objectives with high quality.
- Implementing appropriate evaluation procedures at the start, middle, and end of each lesson.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Human relations skills are regarded as a manifestation of an executive's capacity to collaborate effectively with others. This necessitates their ability to comprehend, motivate, and lead individuals or groups. Additionally, human relations skills encompass the capacity to delegate tasks, foster the growth of subordinates and staff, and effectively evaluate and guide the behavior of subordinates toward improved performance (Onchoke et al., 2015).

These skills are particularly challenging because they entail considering differences in attitudes, emotions, and cultural attributes among peers, subordinates, and superiors (Jones and George, 2009). Human relations skills are deemed crucial for management at all levels, with the greatest demand expected among first-line supervisors and middle-level principals who have the highest number of interactions with subordinates. Administrative leaders' human relations skills are integral for fostering innovation and enhancing organizational performance (Mabel, 2013).

Effective management requires a balanced proficiency in technical, human, and conceptual aspects of leadership (Jones and George, 2009; Samson and Draft, 2009). Creating an environment conducive to effective, gratifying, and growth-enhancing human interactions necessitates the efficient application of human skills (Carmeli, 2006; Pfeffer, 2008; Winter, 2003). Therefore, Anho (2018) stressed the importance of enhancing interpersonal and human relationship skills to enhance the institutional climate and administrative commitment because an improved relationship between management and staff leads to increased staff (lecturers') productivity.

Leaders are anticipated to fulfill the roles of task facilitators, mediators, and motivators for their employees (Carmeli, 2006). Furthermore, human relations and administrative skills are vital for formulating and implementing sustainable and competitive business strategies (Guest, 2007; Harvey and Buckley, 2002; Mabel, 2013; Rukstad and Collins, 2001). Organizational performance relies significantly on the relationships between workers and managers, with leaders playing a

pivotal role in achieving optimal organizational performance (Carmeli, 2006). Productivity and efficiency are contingent on a manager's abilities, skills, and performance (Carmeli, 2006). Porter and Ketels (2003) also highlighted that the quality of management is the foremost determinant of economic performance. Hence, for schools to excel, Heads of Departments (HODs) should possess human relations skills to motivate staff and organize tasks within their departments.

According to Samson and Draft (2009), human relations skills are also known as interpersonal skills. These skills involve the ability to work effectively with people based on an understanding of their beliefs, group dynamics, effective communication methods, as well as their motives, attitudes, and emotions. Human relations skills are essential for a leader to influence team or group members to collaborate toward achieving organizational goals and objectives.

Guest (2007) asserted that proficiency in human skills involves a leader's ability to not only understand their own perspectives on various matters but also to be attuned to the thoughts and opinions of others. Consequently, leaders with a higher level of interpersonal skills are more adept at aligning their ideas with those of others, especially when this alignment contributes to achieving organizational goals more efficiently. Such leaders exhibit greater sensitivity and empathy toward the motivations of their team members, foster a trustful atmosphere among their followers, and take into account the needs and motivations of others when making decisions to achieve organizational goals.

Mullins (2006) described the importance of a manager possessing a blend of technical competence, social and human skills, and conceptual ability. Social and human skills encompass the capacity to interact effectively with people, which is a crucial attribute across all levels of management. These skills pertain to interpersonal relationships in working with and through other individuals, and they involve exercising sound judgment. Management distinctively involves the ability to maximize the effective use of an organization's human resources, which necessitates successful teamwork and the direction and leadership of staff to achieve coordinated efforts.

According to Vishwanath (2012), human skills encompass the ability to work with, understand, and motivate individuals, both as individuals and within groups. This necessitates being sensitive to the concerns and issues of others. Latif (2002) characterizes human skills as the capacity to understand oneself, work effectively with others, comprehend and motivate others to achieve results. This includes developing self-awareness, managing personal stress, providing coaching and counseling, motivating, handling conflicts, and empowering others. Human relations

skills are also referred to as interpersonal skills, which are the capacity to work effectively with people, understand them, communicate, and collaborate with them. These skills enable principals to lead, motivate, and foster team spirit, particularly in the school management context.

Bolei (2012) conducted research focusing on staff perceptions of the head staff's practice of human relation skills in secondary school management and how it influenced their commitment to work, specifically in Baringo district, Kenya. The study aimed to explore staff perceptions of the head staff's human relations skills practice in secondary school management and its impact on staff commitment to their work. The research targeted all secondary school staff in Baringo district. A survey research design was employed, with purposive sampling to select six secondary schools and subsequently 90 staff members. The study's independent variables included the head staff's practice of human skills, while the dependent variables encompassed staff perceptions of their commitment to school work, gender, teaching experience, and the type of school, forming moderator variables. The research instruments were validated by the supervisor and other experts in the department of Curriculum, Instruction, and Educational Management at Egerton University. The Cronbach's reliability coefficient for the instruments was 0.9211, exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.7. The data was collected using a staff questionnaire (TQ) that assessed staff perceptions of the head staff's human skills practice. The data was organized on a five-point Likert scale and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, with the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) employed for analysis. The hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of statistical significance. The findings indicated a mild relationship between staff perceptions of the head staff's practice of human relations skills and their commitment to school work. While this study shares some similarities with the present research, the key difference lies in the administrative skills studied, as the current study investigates a broader range of skills, including human skills. Moreover, this study is conducted in a different environment, focusing on Delta and Bayelsa States in Nigeria, making it distinct and valuable.

METHODOLOGY

The study utilizes an ex-post facto research design, employing a co-relational and descriptive survey method on 17,024 population comprising, which includes 16,384 teachers and 640 principals from Bayelsa and Delta States.

The sample size includes 812 participants, The random sampling technique was applied to obtain 90 principals from Bayelsa state and 231 from Delta State amounting to 321 principals.

Similarly, 120 teachers from Bayelsa State and 371 teachers from Delta State amounting to 491 teachers.

The research instrument is a self-constructed questionnaire developed based on the integrated quality management constructs originally formulated by Saraph, Benson, and Schroeder (1989). Additionally, it drew upon information from relevant literature in this field, specifically created for this study. The questionnaire was aptly named the "Principals' Total Quality Human Relations Management Skills and Teachers' Pedagogical Output Questionnaire" (PTQHRMTPOQ).

To gather responses, the questionnaire employed a Likert 4-point rating scale were "Strongly Agree" (SA) with a value of 4 points, "Agree" (A) with 3 points, "Disagree" (D) with 2 points, and "Strongly Disagree" (SD) with 1 point. The questionnaire was structured into two main sections. Section A aimed to collect background information which included personal details. Section B of the questionnaire was designed to assess the Principals' Total Quality Human Relations Management Skills and Teachers' Pedagogical Output in public secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States. The face and content validity of the instrument was assessed through expert judgment.

The reliability of this instrument was assessed using both the split-half method and the Cronbach alpha statistics.

To evaluate reliability, the researcher administered the instrument to a randomly selected groups of forty-five (45) secondary school principals in Edo State, chosen due to its shared historical, geopolitical, social, and economic characteristics with Bayelsa and Delta States, all of which belong to the same South-South Geopolitical zone in the Niger-Delta region of Nigeria.

The scores obtained from the responses were tabulated and analyzed. The Cronbach alpha statistic yielded 0.79 reliability coefficient indices deemed reliable and thus were utilized for the study.

The researcher utilized descriptive statistics, specifically mean scores and standard deviation, the correlation coefficients to determine the existence of relationships among the variables to address the research question with a mean score (\bar{X}) rating of 2.50 or higher considered as the benchmark for acceptance. Additionally, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics were applied to assess the significance of the relationship in the formulated hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The results were presented and analyzed in tabular form.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF DATA/FINDINGS

Research Question: What is the relationship between principals’ use of Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relations skills and Teachers’ Pedagogical Output in public secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States?

Table 1: Correlational coefficient of determination analysis between principals’ use of Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relations skills and Teachers’ Pedagogical Output in public secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States

State	Variables	N	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r%	Remarks
Bayelsa	Principals use of conceptual skills	180	2.72	1.56	0.80	0.64	64	Positive relationship
	Teachers Pedagogical Output		2.59	0.91				
Delta	Principals use of conceptual skills	505	2.75	0.82	0.60	0.36	36	Positive relationship
	Teachers Pedagogical Output		2.60	0.85				
Bayelsa and Delta	Principals use of conceptual skills	685	2.74	1.19	0.70	0.49	49	Positive relationship
	Teachers Pedagogical Output		2.60	0.88				

Source: Researchers’ Field Work 2023

Table 1 illustrates the analysis of correlation coefficient of determination regarding the relationship between principals' use of Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relation skills and teachers' pedagogical output in secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States.

For Bayelsa State (N = 180), the mean for principals' use of Total Quality Management human relations/interpersonal skills is 2.72, with a standard deviation (SD) of 1.56. In contrast, teachers' pedagogical output has a mean score of 2.59, with an SD of 0.91. The computed r (correlation coefficient) value is 0.80, indicating a positive relationship between principals' utilization of Total Quality Management human relations/interpersonal skills and teachers' pedagogical output in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The r² (coefficient of determination)

high value is 0.64, meaning that principals' use of human relations/interpersonal skills contribute 64% to teachers' pedagogical output in Bayelsa State.

The analysis of data from Delta State (N = 505) principals' use of Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relations skills has a mean of 2.75 and an SD of 0.82 while teachers' pedagogical output has a mean score of 2.60, with an SD of 0.85. The computed r value for Delta State is 0.60, indicating a positive relationship between principals' use of Total Quality Management human relations/interpersonal skills and teachers' pedagogical output in secondary schools in Delta State. The r^2 value of 0.36 though low, shows that principals' utilization of human relations/interpersonal skill contribute 36% to teachers' pedagogical output in Delta State.

When the data from both Bayelsa and Delta States are combined (N = 685), the analysis indicates that the mean scores for principals' use of Total Quality Management human relations/interpersonal skills is 2.74, with an SD of 1.19, while the mean score for teachers' pedagogical output is 2.60, with an SD of 0.88. The computed r value is 0.70, indicating a positive relationship between principals' use of Total Quality Management human relations/interpersonal skills and teachers' pedagogical output in secondary schools in both Bayelsa and Delta States. The r^2 value of 0.45 suggests that principals' use of human relations/interpersonal skills contribute 45% to teachers' pedagogical output in both states.

Decision: The analysis demonstrates a positive relationship between principals' use of Total Quality Management human relations/interpersonal skills and teachers' pedagogical output in public secondary schools in both Bayelsa and Delta States. The degree of influence varies between the two states and when both states are considered together. The relationship is moderately high.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between principals’ use of total quality management human/interpersonal relationship skills and teachers’ pedagogical output in secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient analysis between principals’ use of total quality management human/interpersonal relationship skills and teachers’ pedagogical output in secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States

State	Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	r-cal	r-crit	Level of sig.	Remark
Bayelsa	Principals’ use of Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relationship Skills	180	2.72	1.56	179	0.80	0.087	0.05	Significant relationship
	Teachers’ pedagogical output		2.59	0.91					
Delta	Principals use of Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relationship Skills	505	2.75	0.82	504	0.68	0.087	0.05	Significant relationship
	Teachers’ pedagogical output		2.61	0.88					
Bayelsa and Delta	Principals’ use of Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relationship Skills	685	2.74	1.49	684	0.56	0.087	0.05	Significant relationship
	Teachers’ pedagogical output		2.60	0.88					

Significant at 0.05 alpha level

Table 2 displays the analysis of test of hypothesis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient results, indicating the relationship between principals' utilization of total quality management human/interpersonal relationship skills and teachers' pedagogical performance in secondary schools in both Bayelsa and Delta States.

In Bayelsa State (N = 180), the mean score for principals' utilization of Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relationship skills is 2.72, with a high standard deviation (SD)

Received: 2 March 2024

Revised: 12 March 2024

Final Accepted 22 March 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10854615>

of 1.56. Conversely, the mean score for teachers' pedagogical performance is 2.59, with a more modest SD of 0.91. The analysis is based on 179 degrees of freedom, with a calculated coefficient 'r' value of 0.80. The critical 'r' value stands at 0.087 at a significance level of $P>0.05$.

According to the analysis, the calculated coefficient 'r' value of 0.80 surpasses the critical value of 0.087. This indicates a significant relationship between principals' utilization of total quality management human/interpersonal relationship skills and teachers' pedagogical performance in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

In Delta State (N = 505), the table reveals that the mean score for principals' utilization of Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relationship skills is 2.75, while the mean score for teachers' pedagogical performance is 2.60, accompanied by an SD of 0.85. The analysis is conducted with 505 degrees of freedom, and the calculated coefficient 'r' value is 0.68. The critical 'r' value remains at 0.087 at a significance level of $P>0.05$.

Following this analysis, the calculated coefficient 'r' value of 0.68 exceeds the critical value of 0.087, suggesting a significant relationship between principals' utilization of total quality management human/interpersonal relationship skills and teachers' pedagogical performance in Delta State.

The table also discloses the combined analysis for Bayelsa and Delta States (N = 685). The mean score for principals' utilization of total quality management human/interpersonal relationship skills is 2.60, with an SD of 0.86. The analysis involves 684 degrees of freedom, and the calculated coefficient 'r' value is 0.56, while the critical 'r' value remains at 0.087, with a significance level of $P>0.05$.

The analysis indicates that the calculated coefficient 'r' value of 0.56 is higher than the critical value of 0.087 at a significance level of $P>0.05$. This suggests a significant relationship between principals' utilization of total quality management human/interpersonal relationship skills and teachers' pedagogical performance in secondary schools in both Bayelsa and Delta States. Consequently, the null hypothesis 6 is refuted.

This finding runs counter to the works of Uchendu, Anijaobi, and Nkane (2013), who suggest that administrative styles of principals can vary, leading to differences in teachers' pedagogical output in different institutions and schools. Additionally, it contrasts with Anho's (2020) observation that various policies, procedures, motivational factors, communication

practices, working conditions, interpersonal relationships, and levels of involvement in decision-making can all influence teachers' motivation and, consequently, their teaching effectiveness.

The discovery arisen in response the to research question, which was meticulously analyzed in table 1 indicates the presence of a significant relationship between the utilization of Total Quality Management (TQM) Human/Interpersonal Relations Skills by Principals and the Pedagogical Performance of Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa and Delta States.

To ascertain the significance of this relationship, the hypothesis was tested. The outcome, as presented in table II, unequivocally reveals a positive and statistically significant correlation between Principals' use of Total Quality Management Human/Interpersonal Relations Skills and the Pedagogical Performance of Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa and Delta States.

This finding lends support to the results of a research conducted by Bolei (2012), which focused on staff perceptions of head-staff human skills. **BORD** established a positive relationship commitment is pivotal in fostering performance, as it reflects the willingness of individuals to invest personal resources in their teaching tasks. A committed teacher is dedicated and takes job seriously, ultimately leading to enhanced performance. Such commitment is indispensable for achieving quality education.

Furthermore, this finding aligns with the research findings of Kami (2020) on principals' management skills and the quality of teaching by secondary school teachers in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria, which encompassed Bayelsa, Delta, and Edo States. Kami's research highlighted the significant relationship between principals' personal relationship skills, among other skills, and the quality of teaching delivered by teachers.

Decision: Under Human Relations Interpersonal Skills, successful principals excel in working cooperatively with others. They display a deep understanding of subordinates, inspire and motivate workers, provide guidance in the delegation of responsibilities, contribute to staff development and education, conduct effective and timely performance appraisals, manage subordinate behavior to enhance the quality of output, consider individual differences in employees' attitudes, actively engage workers in decision-making processes, and acknowledge the influence of cultural characteristics in achieving organizational objectives, among other competencies.

Additionally, the principles of human/interpersonal relations skills are indispensable for involving all staff in decision-making processes, ensuring their ideas are heard, being sensitive and empathetic to what motivates others, and effectively harnessing collaboration in a technological context.

Summary of Findings

From the presentation, analysis and discussion of data, the following findings emerge that;

1. The correlation coefficient value of 80 and the correlation of determination value of 64% in Bayelsa State is higher than the correlation coefficient value of 60 and correlation determination of 36% in Delta State. This means the relationship between principal use of human/interpersonal relations and teachers' pedagogical performance is also higher in Bayelsa State than Delta State.
2. Some secondary school principals are reluctant to adopt the use of total quality management skills of human/interpersonal relations hence teachers' pedagogical performance is affected in such state.
3. There is a positive significant relationship between the use of principals' Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relations skills and Teachers' Pedagogical Output in public secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta States.

Conclusion

Total quality management involves the use of human/interpersonal relations skills which positively influence teachers' pedagogical performance in public secondary schools in Bayelsa and Delta State.

TQM involves application of quality management principals, promoting continuous quality improvement of all members, soliciting for cooperation of all stakeholders to satisfy the needs, objectives and expectations of clients and the organization. TQM is quality centric, customer focused, team driven, seminar led and human relations oriented.

Human/interpersonal relations involves interpersonal, cordial, and cooperative relations between the administrators, and teachers. It also involves teachers' welfare, including salary, open quality communication, conducive climate of the work environment, collaboration, understanding, and good leadership.

Pedagogical skills comprises all efforts made by teachers to attain intended quality educational results of students including preparing and utilizing, good class management, suitable

quality teaching methods, lesson delivering, employing suitable teaching resources and appropriate evaluation among others.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Principals and teachers in secondary schools should shift their perspective on Total Quality Management (TQM) skills especially human/interpersonal relations skills, recognizing that they are beneficial not only for businesses but also for educational institutions.
2. School administrators, particularly principals, should actively adopt and enhance their Total Quality Management human/interpersonal relations skills, as these have a positive impact on teachers' pedagogical performance.
3. School administrators and management should work towards attaining the indices of total quality management human/interpersonal skills such as; collaborative planning, teamwork, participative decision-making, staff welfare, delegation of responsibilities to teachers, implement feedback mechanisms, integrate and coordinate all activities within the school to enhance teachers' pedagogical output.

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